

Enhancing Rural Women's Entrepreneurship: The Role of Family Structure and Employment Factors within Farmer Producer Organizations (FPOs)

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Abstract - This study explores the role of Farmer Producer Organizations (FPOs) in empowering rural women entrepreneurs across the Chittoor, Kurnool, Ananthapur, and Tirupati districts of Andhra Pradesh. Focusing on a sample of 480 female producers, the research examines the impact of family structure, number of dependents, and employment dynamics within families on the entrepreneurial activities of these women. The study aims to understand how these socio-economic factors influence the effectiveness of FPOs in fostering economic empowerment and sustainability for rural women. Through quantitative analysis, the research highlights the correlation between family dynamics and the success of women entrepreneurs within FPOs, offering insights into the specific challenges and opportunities faced by these women in their entrepreneurial journey. The findings suggest that supportive family structures and a balanced number of dependents significantly enhance women's participation and success in FPO-led initiatives. Additionally, the study provides recommendations for policymakers and stakeholders on strengthening FPO frameworks to better accommodate the needs of rural women entrepreneurs, thereby promoting inclusive growth and gender equity in rural economies.

Keywords-Andhra Pradesh, Employment, Empowerment, Farmer producer Organization (FPO), Inclusion

I. INTRODUCTION

Farmer Producer Organizations (FPOs) have emerged as a pivotal strategy for empowering small and marginalized farmers in India. As a specific type of Producer Organization (PO), an FPO is composed of farmers who are the primary producers, including those involved in agriculture, non-farm products, and artisan goods. Supported by the Small Farmers' Agribusiness Consortium (SFAC), FPOs aim to aggregate small and landless farmers to enhance their market linkages, thereby improving their income and economic resilience. By providing end-to-end services, including marketing, technical support, processing, and cultivation inputs, FPOs have proven instrumental in overcoming the challenges faced by small-scale producers. The core objective of FPOs is to bolster farmers' competitiveness and their ability to capitalize on emerging market opportunities. This is achieved through various operations such as the supply of seeds, fertilizers, machinery, and the provision of training, financial support, and technical advice. A key advantage of FPOs lies in their ability to eliminate intermediaries in agricultural marketing, enabling producers to benefit from economies of scale and enhancing their bargaining power as bulk suppliers. FPOs are founded on the principles of voluntary participation, inclusivity, and member control, with a focus on providing education and training to ensure the effective development of the organization. The promotion of FPOs is often guided by the 'One District One Product'

initiative, which encourages specialization, branding, and market expansion. Particularly in aspirational districts, the formation of FPOs is prioritized to ensure equitable growth and empowerment at the grassroots level. This study delves into the impact of FPOs on rural women entrepreneurs in the districts of Chittoor, Kurnool, Ananthapur, and Tirupati, with a focus on 480 female producers. By analyzing the influence of family structure, the number of dependents, and employment dynamics, this research aims to uncover the specific challenges and opportunities that these women face in their entrepreneurial endeavors. Through this lens, the study seeks to provide insights into how FPOs can be further strengthened to support the economic empowerment of rural women, ultimately contributing to inclusive and sustainable rural development. This study delves into the impact of FPOs on rural women entrepreneurs in the districts of Chittoor, Kurnool, Ananthapur, and Tirupati, with a focus on 480 female producers. By analyzing the influence of family structure, the number of dependents, and employment dynamics, this research aims to uncover the specific challenges and opportunities that these women face in their entrepreneurial endeavors. Through this lens, the study seeks to provide insights into how FPOs can be further strengthened to support the economic empowerment of rural women, ultimately contributing to inclusive and sustainable rural development.

LITERATURE REVIEW

- Rozita Abdul Mutalib, Et al.(2015) described Women Entrepreneurship programs in Malaysia and the government initiatives and its impact on wealth generation.
- Multana Begum, Et al.(2019) researched on poultry farming in Bangladesh, proposed women have limited capacity to generate employment for other women.
- Susan Kaaria Et al.(2016) has stated that Producer organizations have become crucial service providers to nurture rural poor women's participation and focus on leadership efforts.
- Carr Et al.(2010) proposed most women work for approximately 16 hours a day.
- Oxfam (2013 &2018) mentioned that age, social status and previous experience in organizations are the other factors that can affect women's participation in producer organizations. Governments and businesses view women owned producer organizations as a useful mechanism for reducing poverty and improving small producer livelihoods
- Anjana Rani(2016) in her research about Lijjat Papad stated that education is not the criteria for a successful business.
- Yogita Sharma(2013) in her research article mentioned that Women enter entrepreneurship due to economic factors pushing women to do something independently.
- Popoola Mufutau Akanmu Et al.(2018) studied the Impact of Cooperative Microfinance on the Performance of Women Entrepreneurship in Nigeria.
- Olateju Et al.(2017) concluded that women are often found in entrepreneurial activities because of their reproductive role, which are a hindrance to white collar jobs.
- Musa(2014) notes that economic growth is a long-term process of sustainable rise where women are included.
- Khan Et al.(2021) used upper echelons theory which demonstrates that the influence of top women management behavior personalities affect organizational performance.
- Robert(2015) described though women contribute significantly to the workforce in agriculture but still carry the main burden of childcare and household chores.

- Sukhpal Singh Et al.(2013) researched Southern Indian states deposit more successful FPO businesses when compared to Northern India.
- EugeniaRoscaa Et al.(2020) had stated that Women social entrepreneurs employ technological innovations and inclusive strategies to improve the quality of life .
- Herbel Et al.(2012) reviewed that producer organizations can provide enhanced access to natural resources and facilitate small producers' participation in policy-making.
- Coleman Et al.(2012) have documented that improved participation of women lead to conservation of natural resources.
- Manfre Et al.(2012) found that the socio-cultural barrier that hinders women's participation and particularly leadership in producer organizations.
- Gotschi Et al.(2009) in Mozambique described married women have less possibility to engage in outdoor activities.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

This study has three objectives as below:

- I. To Enhance Strategic Capabilities among FPO Members
- II. To elevate producers into higher leadership roles preparing for the future
- III. To Promote Diversification and Skill Enhancement Across Business Roles

METHODOLOGY

The present study is both descriptive and analytical. The researcher determined that primary data would be most suitable for this research and employed a descriptive approach to explain the findings. Additionally, the study uses both primary and secondary data sources. Primary data were gathered through a finalized interview schedule from selected members of Farmer Producer Organizations (FPOs). Secondary data were obtained from various sources, including websites, textbooks, journals, and previously conducted studies, to support the hypotheses. The interview schedule was meticulously designed to achieve the study's objectives, incorporating both original questions and elements adapted from previous research. The data collected from the FPO members were then subjected to validity and reliability tests. The researcher ensured accuracy by computing the validity and conducting a pilot study. The researcher, hailing from the Tirupati District of Andhra Pradesh, focused on the state's 613 operational FPOs. Given the large number of FPOs and their members, the convenience sampling technique under the non-probability sampling method was chosen. A sample size of 480 members was determined using a margin of error calculator. The sample was drawn from three districts—Anantapur, Chittoor, and Kurnool—each hosting more than 50 FPOs. From these districts, the researcher randomly selected 40 FPOs and chose four members from each, resulting in a total sample size of 480 members.

DATA ANALYSIS & FINDINGS

The following table shows the socio-economic profile variables of the selected women members of the FPOs.

TABLE I

Socio economic Profile Variables		Count	Percentage
Nature of Residents	Rural	253	52.71%
	Semi-Urban	227	47.29%
	Total	480	100.00%
Monthly Family Income	Upto Rs.15000	115	23.96%
	15001 – 30000	177	36.88%
	30001 – 45000	113	23.54%
	Above Rs.45000	75	15.63%
	Total	480	100.00%

Monthly Average Income of Individual	Upto Rs. 6000	105	21.88%
	6001 – 12000	191	39.79%
	12001- 18000	155	32.29%
	Above Rs.18000	29	6.04%
	Total	480	100.00%
Nature of Business in the FPO	Service provider	80	16.70%
	Production and Sales of agricultural products	108	22.50%
	Production of agricultural only	75	15.60%
	Buying and Selling of agricultural products	94	19.60%
	Sales only	93	19.40%
	Artisan	16	3.30%
	Food processing business	14	2.90%
	Total	480	100.00%

Source: Primary Data

NATURE OF RESIDENTS

The researcher also gathered information regarding the residence of the selected FPO members. The data revealed that 52.71% of the 480 members reside in rural areas, while the remaining 47.29% live in semi-urban areas. This indicates that the majority of the members (52.71%) are located in rural areas.

MONTHLY FAMILY INCOME

The pollster also analyzed the monthly family income of the selected FPO members. The data revealed that among the 480 members, 23.96% have a family income of up to ₹15,000, 36.88% have a family income between ₹15,001 and ₹30,000, 23.54% earn between ₹30,001 and ₹45,000, and the remaining 15.63% have a family income above ₹45,000. This indicates that the largest group (36.88%) has a monthly family income ranging from ₹15,001 to ₹30,000.

MONTHLY AVERAGE INCOME OF INDIVIDUAL

The study also examined the average monthly income of individual FPO members. The data revealed that among the 480 members, 21.88% earn up to ₹6,000 per month, 39.79% earn between ₹6,001 and ₹12,000, 32.29% earn between ₹12,001 and ₹18,000, and the remaining 6.04% earn above ₹18,000 per month. Notably, the majority of members (39.79%) have an individual monthly income ranging from ₹6,001 to ₹12,000.

NATURE OF BUSINESS IN THE FPO

The researcher conducted an extensive study to understand the nature of the businesses run by FPO members. The data revealed that among the 480 members, 16.70% are engaged in service provider businesses, 22.50% are involved in both cultivating and selling agricultural produce, 15.60% focus solely on cultivation, 19.60% are engaged in buying and selling agricultural products, 19.40% serve as sellers only, 3.30% are artisans, and the remaining 2.90% are involved in food processing. Notably, the largest group (22.50%) is engaged in both cultivating and selling agricultural produce.

LEADERSHIP ROLE AND CHALLENGES IN THE FPO

The researcher has also studied the leadership role played by the members of the FPOs and Challenges in the FPO. Likert's five points scaling technique is used to grouping the six variables. The details are presented in the following table

TABLE II

LEADERSHIP ROLE AND CHALLENGES IN THE FPO

Business administrator role	Count	18	197	223	23	19	480
	%	3.75%	41.04%	46.46%	4.79%	3.96%	100.00%
Humanistic person role	Count	24	208	202	23	23	480
	%	5.00%	43.33%	42.08%	4.79%	4.79%	100.00%
Business expert role	Count	19	198	242	13	8	480
	%	3.96%	41.25%	50.42%	2.71%	1.67%	100.00%
Business strategist role	Count	18	102	183	168	9	480
	%	3.75%	21.25%	38.13%	35.00%	1.88%	100.00%
Business challenger role	Count	48	96	151	166	19	480
	%	10.00%	20.00%	31.46%	34.58%	3.96%	100.00%
Level of Challenges in the FPOs	Count	57	140	82	98	103	480
	%	11.88%	29.17%	17.08%	20.42%	21.46%	100.00%

Source: Computed Data

1. Business Administrator Role

Among the 480 FPO members, 3.75% occupy the business administrator role at a very high level, 41.04% at a high level, 46.46% at a medium level, 4.79% at a low level, and 3.96% at a very low level. The majority (46.46%) occupy this role at a medium level.

2. Humanistic Person Role

Regarding the humanistic person role, 5.00% of the 480 members occupy this role at a very high level, 43.33% at a high level, 42.08% at a medium level, 4.78% at a low level, and 4.80% at a very low level. Most members (43.33%) occupy this role at a high level.

3. Business Expert Role

In terms of the business expert role, 3.96% of the 480 members occupy this role at a very high level, 41.25% at a high level, 50.42% at a medium level, 2.71% at a low level, and 1.67% at a very low level. The majority (50.42%) occupy this role at a medium level.

4. Business Strategist Role

For the business strategist role, 3.75% of the 480 members occupy this role at a very high level, 21.25% at a high level, 38.13% at a medium level, 35.00% at a low level, and 1.88% at a very low level. Most members (38.13%) occupy this role at a medium level.

5. Business Challenger Role

Regarding the business challenger role, 10.00% of the 480 members occupy this role at a very high level, 20.00% at a high level, 31.46% at a medium level, 34.58% at a low level, and 3.96% at a very low level. The majority (34.58%) occupy this role at a low level.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Targeted Training Programs:

- Given that a significant number of FPO members occupy roles at medium or lower levels in business administration, business strategy, and expertise, it would be beneficial to develop targeted training programs. These programs should focus on enhancing skills in these areas, helping members move from medium to high proficiency in their respective roles.

2. Strengthening Business Strategy Capabilities:

- With 35% of FPO members currently occupying the business strategist role at a low level, there's a clear need to bolster strategic thinking and planning among members. Workshops or mentoring sessions with experienced strategists could improve their ability to make long-term decisions that drive growth.

3. *Encouraging Leadership Development:*
 - The relatively low percentage of members occupying very high-level roles across different categories indicates a need for leadership development. Creating leadership development programs that focus on decision-making, team management, and innovation could elevate members to higher levels of responsibility within the FPOs.
4. *Promoting Diversification in Business Roles:*
 - The study shows that members are concentrated in certain roles, such as business administration and humanistic roles. Encouraging diversification by promoting other roles like business strategy and challenging roles can help balance the distribution of skills and responsibilities within the FPOs, leading to a more robust organization.
5. *Enhancing Role-Specific Competencies:*
 - Tailored competency development initiatives could be introduced for members based on their current roles. For instance, those in the business expert role could benefit from advanced business analytics and market research training, while those in the business challenger role could be trained in risk management and innovation strategies.
6. *Monitoring and Evaluation:*
 - Regular assessment and feedback mechanisms should be implemented to monitor the effectiveness of any interventions or training programs introduced. This will help ensure that members are progressing in their roles and that the FPOs as a whole are benefiting from these improvements.
7. *Focus on Low-Performing Areas:*
 - Since some roles, like the business strategist and business challenger, have a higher percentage of members at low or very low levels, resources should be allocated to specifically address these gaps. This could involve personalized coaching, peer-to-peer learning, or access to external consultants.
8. *Encourage Collaboration and Knowledge Sharing:*
 - To improve overall effectiveness, FPOs should foster an environment where members can share their experiences and knowledge. Creating forums or regular meetings for members to discuss challenges and strategies can help less experienced members learn from those who are more proficient.

By implementing these recommendations, the FPOs can strengthen their organizational capabilities, improve individual member performance, and ultimately achieve greater success in their collective business endeavors.

CONCLUSIONS

The study provides valuable insights into the roles and competencies of members within Farmer Producer Organizations (FPOs). While a significant number of members are functioning at medium levels in key roles such as business administration, strategy, and expertise, there is a clear opportunity for growth and development. By implementing targeted training programs, enhancing leadership skills, and promoting diversification in business roles, FPOs can empower their members to elevate their performance and take on greater responsibilities.

The emphasis on strengthening strategic capabilities and encouraging role-specific competencies will not only improve individual member outcomes but also contribute to the overall success and sustainability of the FPOs. Regular monitoring and evaluation, coupled

with a focus on collaboration and knowledge sharing, will ensure that these efforts lead to tangible improvements.

In conclusion, by addressing the identified gaps and fostering an environment of continuous learning and development, FPOs can enhance their effectiveness and better serve their members, ultimately contributing to the broader goals of economic growth and agricultural sustainability.

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